

BACTERIOLOGICAL AND MOLECULAR DIAGNOSIS, A SIGNIFICANT CONTRIBUTION TO CHOLERA SURVEILLANCE IN NIGER, 2018–2024

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ABSTRACT

Cholera remains a major public health problem in Niger, characterized by recurrent epidemics, particularly in the border regions of the Lake Chad Basin. Conventional epidemiological surveillance, while essential, has limitations in understanding transmission dynamics and effectively guiding the response. This study aimed to evaluate the contribution of the bacteriological and molecular characterization of *Vibrio cholerae* strains to strengthen surveillance in Niger. Isolates collected between 2018 and 2024 from suspected cases in the main affected regions were analysed. Methods included biochemical identification, serotyping, disc diffusion susceptibility testing, and molecular characterization by PCR for virulence genes (*ctxA*, *tcpA*) and whole genome sequencing (WGS) for phylogenomic analysis. A total of 258 isolates have been confirmed, all of which belonged to serogroup O1, El Tor biotype, Ogawa serotype. All strains carried the *ctxA* and *tcpA* genes. Antibiotic resistance patterns revealed high resistance to tetracycline (85%) and cotrimoxazole (92%), but maintained susceptibility to ciprofloxacin and azithromycin. Phylogenomic analysis on strains from 2018–2024 showed that the Nigerien strains form a distinct clonal group but are closely related to the strains circulating in neighbouring Nigeria, suggesting repeated cross-border introductions as the main driver of outbreaks. These results demonstrate that the integration of molecular surveillance is crucial to identify transmission routes, adapt treatment protocols and guide cross-border prevention strategies. Strengthening laboratory capacity is essential for an effective and targeted cholera response in Niger.

KEYWORDS: Cholera, Bacteriology, Sequencing, *Vibrio cholerae*, Antibiotic resistance, Niger.

INTRODUCTION

Cholera, an acute diarrhoeal infection caused by the ingestion of water or food contaminated with the bacillus *Vibrio cholerae*, remains a global public health threat, disproportionately affecting vulnerable populations in low-income countries.^[1] The seventh cholera pandemic, initiated in 1961 by the El Tor biotype, continues to rage, with endemic outbreaks and explosive epidemics in Africa, Asia and the Americas.^[2] Sub-Saharan Africa, in particular, bears a heavy burden, with frequent outbreaks exacerbated by inadequate water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) infrastructure, conflict and population displacement.^[3, 4]

Niger, a landlocked country in the Sahel, regularly faces cholera outbreaks, mainly concentrated in southern and southeastern border regions. These areas share close hydrographic and socio-economic links with northern Nigeria, a hyper-endemic region for cholera, creating an active cross-border transmission corridor.^[5,6] Epidemiological surveillance in Niger is mainly based on clinical case definition and weekly reporting of suspected cases, with laboratory confirmation for a subset of samples. While this system is vital for early detection of alerts, it provides only limited information about the pathogen itself, its virulence, antimicrobial resistance profile, and genetic links to other regional strains.^[7]

The lack of detailed pathogen data hinders the implementation of targeted control strategies. For example, the evolution of antimicrobial resistance can render standard treatment protocols ineffective, increasing morbidity and mortality.^[8] Moreover, without molecular characterization, it is difficult to distinguish a new strain introduction from a local resurgence from an environmental reservoir or to trace the precise pathways of spread during an outbreak.^[9, 10]

The integration of classical microbiology and advanced molecular typing tools, such as whole genome sequencing (WGS), has revolutionized infectious disease surveillance.^[11] WGS offers unparalleled resolution to study pathogen phylogeny, track transmission in near real-time, identify virulence and resistance genes and understand the evolutionary dynamics of epidemics.^[12, 13] In the context of cholera, these approaches have made it possible to trace the origin and global spread of the seventh pandemic and to characterize successive waves of transmission.^[14] Despite their potential, the application of these technologies remains limited in many African countries, including Niger, due to resource and technical capacity constraints. This study aims to fill this gap by thoroughly characterizing the strains of *V. cholerae* responsible for recent outbreaks in Niger. By combining bacteriological, phenotypic (antibiotic resistance) and genomic analyses, we aim to demonstrate how enhanced laboratory surveillance can provide critical information to improve the cholera response, from clinical management to cross-border prevention strategy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and sample collection

This retrospective study was conducted on epidemiological and laboratory surveillance data recorded between January 2018 and December 2024. The strains of *V. cholerae* came from stool or rectal swabs collected from patients meeting the World Health Organization (WHO) definition of a suspected cholera case.^[15] The samples were collected from cholera treatment centres (CTCs) and health facilities in the most affected regions of Niger as part of the national surveillance system for diseases with epidemic potential. The confirmation, isolation and characterization of isolates were carried out at the Medical and Health Research Center (CERMES), which houses the national reference laboratory for cholera.

Isolation and bacteriological identification

The samples were enriched in alkaline peptone water (APW, pH 8.6) for 6 to 8 hours at 37°C. A 10µL loopful of the enrichment broth was then inoculated on Thiosulfate-Citrate-Bile-Sucrose (TCBS) agar (Thermo Scientific PO2097A). After incubation at 37°C for 18 to 24 hours, suspect yellow colonies (sucrose-fermenting) were subcultured onto a nutrient agar to obtain a pure culture. Identification was confirmed by standard biochemical tests, including the oxidase test (positive) and API 20E galleries (BioMérieux, Marcy-l'Étoile,

France). Strains confirmed as *V. cholerae* were subjected to slide agglutination serotyping with specific polyvalent antisera O1 and O139, as well as monovalent antisera Ogawa and Inaba (Denka Seiken, Tokyo, Japan) to determine the serogroup and serotype.

Antibiotic susceptibility testing

Antimicrobial susceptibility was determined by the disc diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton agar (Kirby-Bauer), in accordance with Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines and the recommendations of the Global Task Force on Cholera Control.^[16, 17] The antibiotics tested include those recommended for the treatment of cholera and those used for resistance monitoring: ampicillin (AMP, 10 µg), cotrimoxazole (SXT, 25 µg), tetracycline (TET, 30 µg), doxycycline (DOX, 30 µg), ciprofloxacin (CIP, 5 µg) and azithromycin (AZM, 15 µg). The diameters of the inhibition zones were measured and interpreted as Sensitive (S), Intermediate (I) or Resistant (R) according to CLSI thresholds. *Escherichia coli* strain ATCC 25922 was used for quality control. Strains that were resistant to at least three different classes of antibiotics were classified as multidrug-resistant (MDR).

Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) and Bioinformatics Analysis

Fifty (50) Niger *V. cholerae* isolates from stool of clinically confirmed cholera cases were analyzed together with those from Cameroon and Nigeria all obtained between 2011 and 2019 during a regional sequencing collaboration in 2019.^[17] DNA was extracted according to the standard protocol of the Qiagen QIAamp DNA Mini Kit with a final elution volume of 200 µL. DNA concentrations were measured with the Qubit Fluorometer 4.0 (Thermo Fisher) according to the standard dsDNA HS protocol. Multiplex PCR was used to confirm the species and detect the main virulence genes. The primers targeted the *ompW* gene (specific to *V. cholerae*), the *rfbO1* and *rfbO139* genes (serogroup-specific), the *ctxA* gene (encoding the A subunit of cholera toxin), and the *tcpA* gene (encoding the major subunit of the toxin-coregulated pilus).^[18] Sequencing and bioinformatics analyses were performed as described elsewhere.^[19-25]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Epidemiological Profile and Disease Burden

Analysis of national surveillance data from 2018 to 2024 reveals an unstable and cyclical epidemiological profile for cholera in Niger, characterized by alternating years of epidemiological silence and major outbreaks (Figure 1). The year 2021 saw an unprecedented peak with 5,591 cases reported, accompanied by a case fatality rate of 2.97%, well above the 1% alert threshold set by the World Health Organization (WHO). The resurgence of the epidemic in 2024, with more than 1,000 cases recorded, confirms the persistence of the threat. The country's continued population growth exacerbates the pressure on already fragile water, hygiene and sanitation

infrastructure, constituting an ongoing risk factor.

Figure 1: Annual Case And Trending Curve Of Cholera Outbreaks In Niger, 2018-2024.

The case fatality rate (Table 1) is a key indicator of the quality and timeliness of case management. The WHO considers a case fatality rate of less than 1% to be an acceptable target in the context of an epidemic. However, the 2018–2024 data show rates well above this threshold during epidemic years. The peak of 2.97% in 2021 is particularly alarming. High rates in 2018

(2.04%), 2022 (2.94%), and 2024 (1.97%) confirm a persistent difficulty in ensuring early and effective patient care. This can be a sign of several challenges, such as difficult geographical access to health centres, delays in consultation, shortages of rehydration solutions and other inputs, or insufficient experience of staff trained in cholera outbreak management.

Year	Number of Suspected Cases	Lethality Rate (%)
2018	3824	2.04
2019	17	0.00
2020	0	0.00
2021	5591	2.97
2022	668	2.94
2023	471	1.27
2024	1066	1.97

Characteristics and Antimicrobial Susceptibility of *Vibrio cholerae* Isolates

From 2018 to 2024, a total of 10,571 suspected cases of cholera were reported at the national level. Of these, 847 stool samples (8%) were received and processed at the National Reference Laboratory for Cholera at CERMES. A total of 391/847 (46%) tested positive, from which 258 strains of *Vibrio cholerae* were isolated. Serotyping revealed that all these strains belonged to serogroup O1, biotype El Tor, and serotype Ogawa. No isolates of serogroup O139 or serotype Inaba were detected. Molecular confirmation by PCR showed that all isolates were positive for the *ompW*, *rfbO1*, *ctxA*, and *tcpA* genes, confirming their epidemic and toxigenic potential. The geographical distribution of confirmed cases corresponded to known outbreak clusters, with a majority of isolates from the Diffa region (n=112,

43.4%), followed by Maradi (n=85, 32.9%) and Zinder (n=61, 23.7%). This is consistent with epidemiological data from the West and Central Africa region, where this lineage has been predominant for decades.^[5, 13]

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing results for the 258 isolates are presented in Table 2. High levels of resistance were observed for cotrimoxazole (92.2%) and tetracycline (85.3%). Moderate resistance was noted for ampicillin (45.0%). In contrast, the vast majority of strains remained susceptible to doxycycline (91.5%), ciprofloxacin (98.8%), and azithromycin (99.6%). Of the total isolates, 118 (45.7%) were resistant to at least three classes of antibiotics and were classified as MDR. The most common resistance profile was AMP-SXT-TET.

Antibiotic	Susceptible (%)	Intermediate (%)	Resistant (%)
Ampicillin (AMP)	55.0	0.0	45.0
Cotrimoxazole (SXT)	7.8	0.0	92.2
Tetracycline (TET)	14.7	0.0	85.3
Doxycycline (DOX)	91.5	1.9	6.6
Ciprofloxacin (CIP)	98.8	0.4	0.8
Azithromycin (AZM)	99.6	0.4	0.0

The observed antibiotic resistance profile is concerning and has direct implications for patient management. Near-widespread resistance to the historically used antibiotics cotrimoxazole and tetracycline renders these molecules obsolete for the empirical treatment of cholera in Niger. Doxycycline, although structurally similar to tetracycline, retains good efficacy, but the emergence of resistance (6.6%) needs to be closely monitored. Fortunately, ciprofloxacin and azithromycin, currently recommended by the WHO as first- and second-line treatments for severe cases, remain highly effective.^[15] Continuous monitoring of susceptibility to these two antibiotics is imperative to anticipate any therapeutic failure.

Phylogenomic Analysis and Transboundary Dynamics

Phylogenomic analysis based on core genome SNPs was performed on 50 Nigerien isolates and 80 isolates from the region (Nigeria, Cameroon, Chad). All the strains analyzed belonged to the 7th pandemic El Tor lineage (7PET). The phylogenetic tree revealed that the 50 strains from Niger formed a distinct monophyletic group, with very low genetic diversity (median difference of 5 SNPs), indicating a clonal origin for outbreaks that occurred between 2018 and 2024.^[17]

This Nigerien clone was found to be closely related to a large cluster of strains isolated in northern Nigeria during the same period, with a genetic distance of only 15-25 SNPs. The strains from the Diffa (2018, 2021) and Maradi (2022, 2023) outbreaks were nearly identical, suggesting rapid spread or multiple introductions from the same transboundary source. The strains from Chad and Cameroon formed distinct clusters, although linked to the same wave of 7PET circulating in West and Central Africa.

The search for antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs) in the genomes corroborated the resistance phenotypes. All tetracycline-resistant isolates carried the *tet(A)* gene. Resistance to cotrimoxazole was associated with the presence of the *sul2* and *dfrA1* genes. These genes were located on a mobile genetic element of the SXT/R391 type, an integrative and conjugative element (ICE) known for its ability to disseminate multidrug resistance in Vibrionaceae.^[26] The presence of this element underlines the risk of rapid dissemination of new resistance determinants.^[27]

The most significant contribution of this study lies in these molecular epidemiology results. The phylogenomic analysis conclusively demonstrated that the cholera outbreaks in Niger between 2018 and 2024 were caused by a single clone, closely related to strains circulating simultaneously in northern Nigeria. This strong genomic connectivity, coupled with the geography of the epidemics (border regions), confirms the hypothesis of a shared epidemiological ecosystem in the Lake Chad Basin.^[6,28] The outbreaks in Niger are likely not isolated

events or resurgences from local environmental reservoirs, but rather extensions of a broader regional transmission dynamic, fuelled by repeated introductions from Nigeria. This finding has major implications for control strategies: national enforcement efforts, while indispensable, will be insufficient without robust cross-border coordination. Surveillance, early warning, vaccination campaigns and WASH interventions need to be planned and implemented jointly with neighbouring countries, particularly Nigeria.^[28] WGS has proven to be a powerful tool, not only for establishing high-resolution epidemiological links but also for predicting antimicrobial resistance patterns. The perfect correlation between the presence of specific resistance genes and the observed phenotypes suggests that genomic surveillance could, in the future, provide rapid and actionable information for clinical management, potentially faster than traditional culture methods.^[11, 12]

Study Limitations

There are a few limitations to our study. First, its retrospective nature and availability-based sample selection may introduce selection bias. Second, although representative, the sequenced isolates do not cover the full spatio-temporal diversity of the outbreaks. Prospective, real-time genomic surveillance would allow for even more detailed tracking of transmission. Finally, the absence of environmental samples did not allow us to study the potential role of local aquatic reservoirs in the persistence of *V. cholerae* between epidemics.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study unequivocally demonstrates the added value of integrating bacteriological and molecular characterization into cholera surveillance in Niger. The identification of antibiotic resistance patterns makes it possible to adapt national treatment guidelines, ensuring effective patient management. Most importantly, genomic epidemiology has clarified the transboundary dynamics of cholera outbreaks, highlighting that Niger is part of a regional focus centered on the Lake Chad Basin. This information is essential to advocate for a supranational control strategy, including coordinated surveillance, cross-border preventive vaccination campaigns and joint investments in WASH infrastructure. Sustainably strengthening the capacity of national laboratories like CERMES for genomic surveillance is a strategic priority to improve preparedness and response to future cholera outbreaks in Niger and the sub-region.

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